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**CIRCULATING IN THE BLOOD DESQUAMATED
ENDOTHELIOCYTES AT THE CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES.
PRELIMINARY COMMUNICATION**

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**ЦИРКУЛЮЮЧІ В КРОВІ ДЕСКВАМОВАНІ ЕНДОТЕЛІОЦИТИ ПРИ
СЕРЦЕВО-СУДИННИХ ЗАХВОРЮВАННЯХ. ПОПЕРЕДНІЙ
ЗВ'ЯЗОК**

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Summary/Резюме

Introduction and aim. We previously found that diabetic angiopathy is accompanied by an increase in the level of desquamated endothelial cells (CECs) circulating in the blood, commensurate with its severity. In this study, we set ourselves the aim of analyzing the level of CECs in patients with cardiovascular pathology and their relationship with the level of blood pressure and routine clinical indicators.

Material and methods. The object of clinical observation were patients with stage II hypertension, who were receiving outpatient treatment. Among them, 23 men (62.3 ± 13.2 ys) and 39 women (65.1 ± 10.6 ys). Concomitant ischemic heart disease was diagnosed in 16 men (70 ± 10 %) and 28 women (72 ± 7 %). The main subject of the study was blood pressure and the level of CECs. In addition, routine general blood analysis and determined metabolic parameters were performed.

Results. Using the method of cluster analysis, the sample was divided into 4 homogeneous groups, different from each other. It was found that in 18 patients of the first cluster, the youngest in the sample, the minimum level of hypertension for the sample occurs against the background of unchanged CECs levels and other registered parameters, instead, it is accompanied by moderate increased creatinemia and a significantly increased rate of erythrocyte sedimentation and a reduced level of hemoglobin and color index. In 18 patients of the second cluster, moderately elevated levels of terminally and markedly changed CECs were found in combination with minimally expressed signs of hyperchromic anemia. In the third cluster ($n = 16$), the levels of terminally and markedly changed CECs are significantly increased in combination with a reduced level of urea and LP index against the background of moderate hyperchromic anemia. Finally, in 10 patients of the fourth cluster, the oldest in the sample, with maximally expressed hypertension, it is accompanied by maximally elevated levels of all three types of CECs against the background of moderate hyperchromic anemia.

Conclusion. Desquamated plasma endothelial cells can be one of the criteria for the severity of hypertonic disease.

Keywords: *desquamated plasma endothelial cells, stage II hypertension, ischemic heart disease.*

Введення і ціль. Раніше нами було встановлено, що діабетична ангіопатія супроводжується підвищенням рівня десквамованих ендотеліальних клітин (ДЕК), цир-

кулуючих у крові, порівняно з її тяжкістю. У цьому дослідженні ми поставили перед собою це проаналізувати рівень ДЕК у пацієнтів із серцево-судинною патологією та їх зв'язок з рівнем артеріального тиску та рутинними клінічними показниками.

Матеріал і методи. Об'єктом клінічного спостереження були пацієнти з гіпертонічною хворобою II стадії, що знаходяться на амбулаторному лікуванні. Серед них 23 чоловіки ($62,3 \pm 13,2$ років) і 39 жінок ($65,1 \pm 10,6$ років). Супутня ішемічна хвороба серця діагностована у 16 чоловіків ($70 \pm 10\%$) і 28 жінок ($72 \pm 7\%$). Основним предметом дослідження являлись артеріальний тиск і рівень ДЕК. Крім того, проводився рутинний загальний аналіз крові і визначали метаболічні показники.

Результати. Методом кластерного аналізу вибірка була розділена на 4 однорідні групи, що відрізняються від другої за віком. Встановлено, що у 18 пацієнтів першого класу, самого молодого у виборі, мінімальний для вибору рівень артеріальної гіпертензії виникає на фоні незмінних рівнів ДЕК та інших зареєстрованих показників, замість цього він супроводжується помірно підвищеною креатинінемією та значно підвищеною швидкістю осідання еритроцитів і зниженим рівнем гемоглобіну та квітів. показателя. У 18 пацієнтів другого кластера виявлені помірно підвищені рівні термінально і виражено змінні ДЕК в поєднанні з мінімально вираженими ознаками гіперхромної анемії. У третьому кластері ($n=16$) рівень термінально і виражено змінних ДЕК достовірно підвищений у поєднанні зі зниженим рівнем сечовини та індексу ЛП на фоні помірної гіперхромної анемії. Наконеч, у 10 пацієнтів четвертого кластера, самого старшого у виборі, при максимально вираженій гіпертензії вона супроводжується максимально підвищеними рівнями всіх трьох типів ДЕК на фоні помірної гіперхромної анемії.

Заключення. Десквамовані плазматичні ендотеліальні клітини можуть бути одним із критеріїв тяжкості гіпертонічної хвороби.

Ключові слова: десквамовані плазматичні ендотеліальні клітини, гіпертензія II стадії, ішемічна хвороба серця.

Introduction

We previously found that diabetic angiopathy is accompanied by an increase in the level of desquamated endothelial cells (CECs) circulating in the blood, commensurate with its severity[1-7]. In this study, we set ourselves the goal of analyzing the level of CECs in patients with cardiovascular pathology and their relationship with the level of blood pressure and routine clinical indicators.

Material and methods

Ethics approval

Tests in patients are conducted in accordance with positions of Helsinki Declaration 1975, revised and complemented in 2002, and directive of National Committee on ethics of scientific researches. During realization of tests from all parent of participants the informed consent is got and used all measures for providing of anonymity of

participants. For all authors any conflict of interests is absent.

Participants

The object of clinical observation were patients with stage II hypertension, who were receiving outpatient treatment at the Center for Primary Health Care No.3 (Odessa) in 2019. Among them, 23 men (62.3 ± 13.2 ys) and 39 women (65.1 ± 10.6 ys). Concomitant ischemic heart disease was diagnosed in 16 men ($70 \pm 10\%$) and 28 women ($72 \pm 7\%$).

Study design and procedure

The main subject of the study was blood pressure and the level of desquamated endothelial cells circulating in the plasma (CECs).

CECs were determined by the method of J. Hladovek.⁸ Platelet-rich plasma (PRP) was prepared by centrifugation (1000 g for

10 min). After the addition of 0.2 ml of Adenosine-Diphosphate to 1 ml of PRP the mixture was shaken mechanically for 10 min. Another centrifugation (1000 g for 10 min) served to remove platelet aggregates. The supernatant was centrifuged at 3000 g for 15 min and the very scanty sediment was carefully suspended in 0.1 ml of 0.9 % NaCl by stirring with a glass rod. From the suspension two platforms of a Goryaev's chamber were filled and cells were counted by the method of phase contrast microscopy using a Micromed XS-3320 binocular microscope, Plan 10 Ph/0.25 lens (10 fold) and eyepieces WF 16X. CECs are well characterized by their size and shape and cannot be mistaken for anything else [8-9]. The cells represent polygonal objects approximately 30-50 μ m in diameter. They often show folded or roiled margins suggesting an extreme thinness of less than 1 μ m. Considering the ratio between the number of cells in platforms and the volume of the Goryaev's chamber, the volume of the resulting suspension and the volume of blood plasma, we calculate the number of CECs in 1 ml of blood plasma [10-16].

In addition, routine general blood analysis were performed and determined metabolic parameters in serum: triglycerides (by a certain meta-periodate method); total cholesterol (by a direct method after the classic reaction by Zlatkis-Zack) and content of him in composition of β -lipoproteins (HDL) (by the enzyme method after precipitation of non- β -lipoproteins); pre- β -lipoproteins (VLDL) (expected by the level of triglycerides); β -lipoproteins (LDL) (expected by a difference between a total cholesterol and cholesterol in composition β - and pre- β -lipoproteins); creatinine (by Jaffe's color reaction by Popper's method); urea (urease method by reaction with phenylhypochlorite); glucose (glucose-oxidase method).

The analysis carried out according to instructions¹⁰ with the use of analyzers "Reflotron" (BRD) and "Pointe-180" (USA) and corresponding sets of reagents.

Statistical analysis

Statistical processing was performed

using a software package "Microsoft Excell" and "Statistica 6.4 StatSoft Inc" (Tulsa, OK, USA).

Results and discussion

For the purpose of correct comparison, registered variables (V) expressed as Z-scores calculated by formula:

$$Z = (V/N - 1)/Cv, \text{ where}$$

N is Mean of Normal (reference) Variable, Cv is Coefficient its variation.

Reference values of routine variables, taking into account sex and age, are borrowed from the handbook [11]. The norms of CECs are taken from the database of our laboratory.

It turned out (Fig. 1) that most variables fluctuate in a wide range, which indicates the heterogeneity of the sample.

Therefore, at the next stage, the sample was divided into groups homogeneous in terms of CECs and blood pressure parameters. Use of Cluster analysis makes possible the simultaneous consideration of all the signs. Considering the totality of characteristics of persons undertaken in their relationship and conditionality of some of these (derivatives) other (main determinants) allows as to make a natural classification that reflects the nature of things, their essence. It is believed that knowledge of the essence of the object is to identify those of its quality properties that actually define the object, distinguish it from other. Clustering cohort of persons was realized by iterative k-means method. In this method, the object belongs to the class Euclidean distance to which is minimal. The main principle of the structural approach to the allocation of uniform groups consists in the fact that objects of same class are close but different classes are distant. In other words, a cluster (the image) is an accumulation of points in n-dimensional geometric space in which average distance between points is less than the average distance from the data points to the rest points.

We have identified 4 clusters.

Members of Cluster No 1 (Contains 18 cases) and Distances from Respective Clus-

ter Center
C1 C2 C3 C4 C5 C7 C8 C9 C13 C16 C19
C28 C32 C35 C36 C38 C40 C60

Distance

61, 130, 137, 115, 41, 125, 172, 59, 86,
152, 43, 75, 79, 91, 60, 125, 94, 147

Members of Cluster No 2 (Contains 18 cases) and Distances from Respective Cluster Center

C6 C10 C11 C12 C14 C17 C18 C20 C21
C23 C24 C25 C30 C37 C39 C41 C43 C50

Distance

149, 158, 195, 91, 214, 147, 94, 21, 101,
162, 111, 168, 129, 63, 113, 59, 104, 130

Members of Cluster No 3 (Contains 16 cases) and Distances from Respective Cluster Center

C15 C27 C33 C34 C42 C45 C46 C49 C52
C53 C54 C55 C56 C57 C59 C62

Distance

133, 103, 89, 109, 108, 58, 55, 93, 123, 15,
99, 196, 88, 79, 134, 64

Members of Cluster No 4 (Contains 10 cases) and Distances from Respective Cluster Center

C22 C26 C29 C31 C44 C47 C48 C51 C58
C61

Distance

184, 173, 178, 121, 131, 113, 180, 129,
102, 28

ber of groups-clusters (4).

It was found (Table 1) that the most characteristic feature of clusters is the level of Markedly altered circulating endothelocytes (ACEC). Terminally ACEC and systolic BP make much smaller but significant contributions to the distribution of the sample into clusters. Instead, the contribution of Initially ACEC is meager and diastolic BP is insignificant.

Clustering, by definition, minimized the variability of variables. It was found that in the patients of the first cluster, the youngest in the sample, hypertension occurs against the background of unchanged CECs levels and other registered parameters, instead, it is accompanied by moderate increased creatinemia and a significantly increased rate of erythrocyte sedimentation and a reduced level of hemoglobin and color index. In the patients of the second cluster, moderately elevated levels of terminally and markedly changed CECs were found in combination with minimally expressed signs of hyperchromic anemia. In the third cluster, the levels of terminally and markedly changed CECs are significantly increased in combination with a reduced level of urea and LP index against the background of moderate hyperchromic anemia. Finally, in patients of the fourth cluster, the oldest in the sample, with maximally expressed hypertension, it is accompanied by maximally elevated levels of all three types of CECs against the background of moderate hyperchromic anemia (Fig. 2).

Further, the registered variables were condensed into 8 patterns (Fig. 3).

In order to identify among the registered parameters, those for which the ACEC&BP clusters differ from each other, a discriminant analysis was performed. The program forward stepwise included in the discriminant model 8 parameters. In addition to CECs and systolic BP by default, the following variables were identified as char-

Cluster Number	Euclidean Distances between Clusters (End_BP.STA)			
	Distances below diagonal		Squared distances above diagonal	
	No. 1	No. 2	No. 3	No. 4
No. 1	0	36020	131120	274792
No. 2	190	0	30955	113213
No. 3	362	176	0	27761
No. 4	524	336	167	0

In the next stage carried Analysis of Variance and ranking variables for coefficient

$$z^2 = Sb^2 / (Sb^2 + Sw^2),$$

$$R = 3,$$

$$F = [Sb^2 (n-k)] / [Sw^2 (k-1)], \text{ where}$$

Sb² is Between Variance; Sw² is Within Variance; n is number of persons (62); k is num-

Fig. 1. Profile of registered sample parameters as a whole

acteristic: HDLP Cholesterol, Hemoglobin, Erythrocytes Sedimentation Rate, and Trombocytes level. The rest of the variables were left out of the model, but some of them still carry identifying information (Tables 2).

Next, the 8-dimensional space of discriminant variables transforms into 3-dimensional space of a canonical roots. For Root 1 $r^* = 0,968$ (Wilks' $\Lambda = 0,0297$; $\chi^2_{(24)} = 193$; $p < 10^{-6}$), for Root 2 $r^* = 0,656$ (Wilks' $\Lambda = 0,4770$; $\chi^2_{(14)} = 40,7$; $p = 0,0002$), for Root 3 $r^* = 0,403$ (Wilks' $\Lambda = 0,838$; $\chi^2_{(6)} = 9,7$; $p = 0,136$). The first root contains 94,1 % of discriminative opportunities, the second 4,7 %, the third 1,2 % only.

Table 3 presents raw and standardized coefficients for discriminant variables. The calculation of the discriminant root values for each person as the sum of the products of raw coefficients to the individual values of discriminant variables together with the constant enables the visualization of each patient in the information space of the roots (Fig. 4).

Table 4 shows the correlation coefficients of discriminant variables with canonical discriminant roots; the cluster centroids of roots; and Z-scores of the discriminant variables. It also includes variables that carry identifying information but were not included in the discriminant model due to duplication/redundancy of information, such as a child's age almost unmistakably indicating his school class.

The localization along the first root axis in the extreme right (positive) zone (Fig. 4)

tients of I cluster, the youngest in the sample, in whom the severity of hypertension is minimal, the levels of markedly and terminally altered CECs are in the lower normal zone, and initially altered CECs as well as glycemia are quite normal, that is, minimal for the sample. Instead, the LP Index is quite normal, that is, the maximum for the sample. The intermediate positions of the members of the other two clusters reflect, as a rule, the intermediate levels of the listed variables.

Additional demarcation of members of II cluster occurs along the axis of the second root. Their lowest position reflects the maximally increased levels of HDLP Cholesterol and Leukocytes and the minimally decreased levels of urea, erythrocytes, and the color index, i.e., in general, the maximum for the sample. On the other hand, in these patients, the Erythrocytes Sedimentation Rate is increased to the smallest extent, the levels of Thrombocytes and Prothrombine Index are normal, and VLDLP Cholesterol is maximally reduced, that is, these parameters are generally minimal for the sample.

In general, all clusters on the planes of two roots are clearly delineated, which is documented by calculating the Mahalanobis distances (Table 5).

The same discriminant parameters can be used to identify the belonging of one or another person to one or another cluster. This purpose of discriminant analysis is realized with the help of classifying functions (Table 7). These functions are special linear combinations that maximize differences be-

of the patients of IV cluster reflects combination of maximum for sampling BP and CECs levels as well as age and glycaemia with maximum decrease in LP index. At the opposite pole are localized pa-

Table 1

Analysis of Variance						
Variables	Between SS	Within SS	η^2	R	F	signif. p
Markedly ACEC	24633148	1817820	0,931	0,965	262	10^{-6}
Terminally ACEC	814331	1536153	0,346	0,589	10,2	10^{-4}
BP systolic	2748	9916	0,217	0,466	5,36	0,003
Initially ACEC	206824	1155111	0,152	0,390	3,46	0,022
BP diastolic	135	11712	0,011	0,107	0,222	0,881

Fig. 2. Profiles of registered parameters of CEC&BP cluster members. Y axis: $Z \pm SE$

Fig. 3. Patterns of registered parameters of CEC&BP cluster members. Y axis: $Z \pm SE$

tween groups and minimize dispersion within groups. An object belongs to a group with the maximum value of a function calculated by summing the products of the values of the variables by the coefficients of the classifying functions plus the constant. In this case, we can retrospectively recognize patients with one mistake only (in II cluster). Overall classification accuracy is 98,4 %.

Conclusion

Desquamated plasma endothelial cells can be one of the criteria for the severity of hypertonic disease.

Funding

No funding

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no competing in-

terests.

Table 2

Data availability

The datasets used and/or analyzed during the current study are open from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Ethics approval

Tests in patients are conducted in accordance with positions of Helsinki Declaration 1975, revised and complemented in 2002, and directive of National Committee on ethics of scientific researches. The study protocol was approved by the Ethical Committee of Ukrainian Scientific Research Institute of Medicine of Transport (protocol No 9/15; 05.08.2024). During realization of tests from all participants the informed consent is got and used all measures for providing of anonymity of participants.

Summary of Stepwise Analysis for Variables, ranked by criterion Lambda

Variables currently in the model	F to enter	p-level	Λ	F-value	p-value
Markedly altered endotheliocytes, c/mL	262	10 ⁻⁶	0,069	262	10 ⁻⁶
Hemoglobin, g/L	3,3	0,028	0,059	59	10 ⁻⁶
HDLP Cholesterol, mM/L	2,1	0,116	0,053	36	10 ⁻⁶
Erythrocytes Sedimentation Rate, mm/h	2,6	0,059	0,046	27	10 ⁻⁶
Terminally altered endotheliocytes, c/mL	2,2	0,096	0,041	22	10 ⁻⁶
Trombocytes, 10 ⁹ /L	2,7	0,052	0,036	19	10 ⁻⁶
Initially altered endotheliocytes, c/mL	1,8	0,163	0,032	16	10 ⁻⁶
Blood Pressure Systolic, mmHg	1,5	0,231	0,030	15	10 ⁻⁶

Table 3

Standardized and Raw Coefficients and Constants for Variables

Variables currently in the model	Coefficients			Standardized			Raw		
	Root 1	Root 2	Root 3	Root 1	Root 2	Root 3	Root 1	Root 2	Root 3
Markedly altered endotheliocytes 0, c/mL	0,969	0,136	0,050	0,0055	0,0008	0,0003			
Terminally altered endotheliocytes 0, c/mL	0,227	-0,591	0,127	0,0014	-0,0036	0,0008			
Blood Pressure Systolic 0, mmHg	0,227	0,030	-0,491	0,0174	0,0023	-0,0376			
Initially altered endotheliocytes 0, c/mL	0,107	-0,321	-0,584	0,0008	-0,0023	-0,0041			
HDLP Cholesterol 0, mM/L	0,075	-0,725	-0,180	0,2438	-2,0368	-0,5895			
Hemoglobin 0, g/L	0,073	-0,434	0,615	0,0057	-0,0335	0,0475			
Erythrocytes Sedimentation Rate 0, mm/h	-0,033	0,842	-0,107	-0,0047	0,1218	-0,0154			
Trombocytes 0, 10 ⁹ /L	-0,014	0,535	0,243	-0,0004	0,0138	0,0063			
	Constants			-13,098	3,0078	-0,446			
	Eigenvalues			15,006	0,756	0,194			
	Cumulative proportions			0,941	0,988	1			

Table 4

Correlations Variables-Canonical Roots, Means of Roots and Z-scores of Variables

Variables currently in the model	Correlations Variables-Roots			I (18)	II (18)	III (16)	IV (10)
	R 1	R 2	R 3				
Root 1 (94,1 %)				-4.77	-0.78	+2.54	+5.92
Markedly altered endotheliocytes	0,948	0,123	0,026	+0.49	+1.43	+2.92	+4.03
Terminally altered endotheliocytes	0,181	-0,135	0,353	+0.18	+1.55	+2.29	+2.52
Blood Pressure Systolic	0,131	0,009	-0,305	+1.83	+2.21	+2.44	+3.16
Initially altered endotheliocytes	0,075	-0,220	-0,544	-0.19	+0.56	0.00	+1.18
Blood Pressure Diastolic				+3.50	+3.42	+3.83	+3.97
Glucose				+0.23	+0.64	+0.63	+0.80
Age				-0.80	-0.20	+0.52	+0.98
LP Index				-0.11	-0.33	-1.56	-1.80
Root 2 (4.7 %)				+0.68	-1.30	+0.49	+0.34
HDLP Cholesterol	-0,018	-0,366	-0,231	+0.60	+1.18	+0.60	+0.90
Hemoglobin	0,052	-0,350	0,573	-1.97	-0.40	-0.69	-1.23
Color Index				-2.76	-1.65	-2.22	-2.77
Urea				-0.31	-0.17	-0.94	-0.58
Leukocytes				-0.11	+0.70	+0.70	+0.38
Erythrocytes Sedimentation Rate	0,002	0,312	-0,077	+2.48	+1.06	+2.46	+2.42
Trombocytes	0,012	0,285	0,346	+0.69	+0.19	+1.03	+0.53
Protrombine Index				+0.29	+0.08	+0.73	+0.38
VLDLP Cholesterol				-0.28	-0.55	-0.25	-0.49

Fig. 4. Scattering of individual values of the first and second discriminant roots of patients of different CEC&BP clusters

Table 5

Squared Mahalanobis Distances between Clusters and F-values (df = 8.5); p for all 10^{-6}

Clusters	I (18)	II (18)	III (16)	IV (10)
I (18)	0	21	58	123
II (18)	20	0	16	51
III (16)	51	14	0	14
IV (10)	79	33	9	0

Table 6

Coefficients and Constants for Classification Functions for Clusters

Endotheliocytes&Blood Pressure Clusters	I	II	III	IV
Variables currently in the model	p = 0,290	p = 0,290	p = 0,258	p = 0,161
Markedly changed endotheliocytes, c/mL	0,0399	0,0603	0,0800	0,0980
Hemoglobin 0, g/L	0,6260	0,7247	0,7115	0,6744
HDLP Cholesterol 0, mM/L	23,66	29,10	25,34	27,29
Erythrocytes Sedimentation Rate 0, mm/h	0,4861	0,2169	0,4129	0,3978
Terminally changed endotheliocytes 0, c/mL	0,0069	0,0199	0,0185	0,0227
Trombocytes 0, $10^9/L$	0,1691	0,1402	0,1679	0,1564
Initial changed endotheliocytes 0, c/mL	0,0175	0,0241	0,0200	0,0283
Blood Pressure Systolic 0, mmHg	1,009	1,068	1,107	1,214
Constants	-182,8	-234,0	-277,7	-339,6

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